

Keywords:

#Reproducibleworkflows,
#KnowledgeGraphs(KGs), #Biologicalentities,
#Chemicalentities, #Entityrepresentations,

Creating FAIR Knowledge Graphs for Open Imaging Data Sharing in EOOSC/COVID-19 Demonstrator

Leveraging OpenBel, pybel, and EOOSC Infrastructures to Facilitate Cross-Domain Research and Reproducible Workflows for Disease Knowledge Graphs

The Service Provider

EU-OS/Fraunhofer ITMP takes the responsibility to consolidate and FAIRify data generated at several EU-OS partner sites for Test Science Project titled 'Open Imaging Data Sharing in EOOSC/COVID-19 as Demonstrator'. Using these data, Knowledge Graphs embedding chemotype-phenotype of diseases are created.

The Challenge

The main scientific challenge is to develop workflows to enable cross-talk between different biological and chemical entities for creating Knowledge Graphs (KGs). Currently, there are discrepancies in entity names and representations. Moreover, the challenge is also to create reproducible workflows such that KGs can be generated within no time. The technical challenge is to find appropriate infrastructures to create the workflow and deploy it in a suitable platform once the KGs are created.

Reagon Karki

Data Manager/Researcher
Fraunhofer ITMP

"The main challenge is to create reproducible workflows for generating Knowledge Graphs (KGs) that enable cross-talk between biological and chemical entities, while also addressing discrepancies in entity names and representations."

The user community

The targeted users for our resource are expected to be mostly researchers studying protein activities, chemoinformaticians and data scientists, mostly involved in COVID-19 and infectious diseases. However, in a longer run, the workflow will be applicable for researchers of any disease field.

The solution

The solution to the challenges were achieved by using open-source framework (i.e. OpenBel) and python package (i.e. pybel) for capturing and representing the underlying semantics of the data. Additionally, we have integrated public curated databases such as ChEMBL, UniProt and OpenTargets to expand the knowledge of chemical and proteins on assays, biological process, functions and pathways and adverse effects. The KG is compliant with FAIR annotations allowing seamless transformation and integration to/with other formats and infrastructures. The EGI notebooks from EOOSC catalogue of services was used as the workspace and tool to deploy the codes and scripts.

The codes are available in the following github repositories.

1. <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-ITMP/BY-COVID-KG>
2. <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-ITMP/mpox-kq>

The links for the resources that are available in EOOSC marketplace are as follows:

1. <https://explore.eoosc-portal.eu/search/software?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.7351393>
2. <https://explore.eoosc-portal.eu/search/software?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.7351221>

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Useful tips & tricks

Although the workflows can be used in mybinder.org, I recommend using the workflows in EGI notebooks. Because, once users sign up for EGI notebook account, they have a personalized workspace to run the scripts. This comes with well supported IT-team in case of issues, easy cloning of github repo, saving workspace anytime and enough space to hold large datasets.

The impact on society

Our main aim of developing the workflows is to make them reproducible such that users can quickly and easily generate KGs for any disease of their interest. One of our main objective is to facilitate researchers with no or little programming skills.

This will enable them to produce KGs with minimal input and make interesting scientific queries to the KG. Moreover, the KGs can be used for downstream analyses such as finding chemicals with similar/dissimilar structures and identifying active assays for protein of interest.

The deployment of the workflow using EGI notebook will bypass tools installation/set-up, meaning that a cloud-based service can be used for all the activities.

Why do I need EOSC ?

EOSC supports the providers with many different features such as monitoring, accounting and long-term sustainability of the resources. Furthermore, providers can use pre-existing tools to deploy their scripts and codes (EGI notebooks in our case). For users, they can go to the marketplace and search any resource with keywords and start using them immediately.

Across disciplines

We are already collaborating and aligning our work with our partners who come from different domains. For example, users of KG can directly access 3D-Bionotes which is a database of protein 3D structures being inside the KG.

Useful material related to this story

COVID-19 Metadata
Findability and
Interoperability

Future developments

Right now, the use of KG workflow needs to prepare some data by the user. For example, the user needs to have files containing list of proteins or chemicals associated with a disease. We intend to remove this preparation for users and provide a feature to type in name of a disease which will then create a KG instantly.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

We would like to see the opportunity to extend the funding period of the project and improve the features of current work.

Future funding model scenarios

The upcoming activities in our current work will be to improve the existing workflow by enabling users to generate KGs at ease with minimal input. Moreover, the deployment of this resource on a cloud-based server will effectively remove the hassle of local installments of tools and packages. We have deployed this in EGI Notebooks: Researchers Edition and are considering upgrading to Community Edition. We have already published a paper highlighting the reproducibility of the workflow using Mpx as a use case. We definitely will publish another paper with the updated and improved features in the KG workflow. Additionally, we aim to offer training and workshops to potential users of our resource. The funding project for our extended work is not yet identified but we see the opportunity to be part of EOSC-Beyond as we seem to align with its scope and objectives.

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